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Editor(s):	Oriol Sallent (UPC)
Author(s)/Contributor(s):	Oriol Sallent, Anna Umbert (UPC) Jesús Gutiérrez (IHP) Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
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List of Acronyms

5GPPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
B5G	Beyond 5G
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
ETSI	European Telecommunication Standards Institute
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
JCR	Journal of Citation Reports
JU	Joint Undertaking
NDT	Network Digital Twin
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RAN	Radio Access Network
SNS	Smart Networks and Services

Executive Summary

The primary aim of BeGREEN D6.3 is to report dissemination and communication actions performed in the first year of the project. The document provides information regarding the communications aspects of the project, such as project's website and social media, and other means of communication and dissemination, such as newsletters. Other dissemination activities, such as scientific publications, workshops, and events during the last 13 months, and those already in plan are introduced. Regarding the external liaison, this document provides consortium participation in SNS and 6GIA working groups. Overall status of the project disseminations compared to the proposed KPIs are provided in the final chapter of the document.

1 Introduction

BeGREEN benefits from a strong consortium and leadership and is committed to an ambitious international and specifically Europe-wide rollout of results into the Beyond 5G (B5G) marketplace following the project. The dissemination and communication strategy defined in D6.1 set the basis, channels, and guidelines to target specific groups covering a wide range of audience, including industry partners, academia, public authorities, standardisation bodies, and end-users. The purpose is to maximise the project outreach ensuring exploitation activities through and after the project's life span. The dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement plans included a range of activities, events, dissemination opportunities and guidelines on how to communicate about the project, as well as KPIs to monitor the relevance and performance of the activities carried out. These plans include specific activities on a national, European, and global levels. All partners in the consortium are contributing to compile a list of relevant events, national activities, and external projects, and are looking at possible opportunities to present the project and set cooperation agreements with external initiatives and organisations.

1.1 Scope of the document

This document describes BeGREEN's dissemination and communication actions performed from the start of the project until the end of M13.

2 Dissemination and Communication Actions

Dissemination activities allow the diffusion of scientific results generated within the project. These results might be of different nature and have different types of target audience. In turn, going beyond the specialised target audience primarily considered in the dissemination activities, BeGREEN has devised a strategy of communicating its concept and results to a wide non-specialised audience. A proper communication strategy is essential to broadly inform about the developments and future impacts of the work carried out in BeGREEN. It is of paramount importance to bring closer the benefits of B5G to the administrations and to the public, conveying the message that they will be beneficial from both economic and societal perspective.

BeGREEN has defined a plan of activities to be performed as described in BeGREEN D6.1 [1]. Table 2-1 presents the list of target KPIs that BeGREEN has established for the different identified actions. The achievements in dissemination and communication are periodically gathered and compared to the targets. The status is discussed among the partners in WP6-specific calls to drive future actions.

Table 2-1 BeGREEN Targets on Dissemination and Communication

Type of Action	Target KPI	Audience
Website and social media	At least 2 newsletters per year, targeting at least 200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn, 3000 access to website, 10 videos posted on YouTube channel	Wide public
Scientific publications	At least 15	Research community
Organisation of highly directed workshops	At least 2 workshops as organisers (1 as lead) At least 3 workshops as participants	Research community, Communications industry, Vertical users
Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives	At least 5 participations	Communications industry
Industry exhibitions	At least participation in 10 industrial events with project visibility	Communications industry, Vertical users
Dissemination through training and personal mobility	At least 3 actions	Research community
Datasets published	At least 2	Research community

2.1 Website and social media

2.1.1 Project website

BeGREEN hosts a comprehensive, regularly updated, public website. It contains all relevant project information such as the global vision and objectives, its relation to 6GIA, SNS JU and other projects in the same domain, and the BeGREEN consortium. The site provides access to the public deliverables of BeGREEN, as well as standardisation results, publications, and public materials, such as flyers, posters, and other collateral. The site news channel provides an overview of BeGREEN events and other relevant events. A database, under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, has been built and a newsletter will be sent every four six months on average. The official webpage address is (www.sns-begreen.com). Figure 2-1, and Figure 2-2 present the main page and its project description section, and Figure 2-3 shows the news section.

Figure 2-1 BeGREEN webpage main page screenshot

Figure 2-2 BeGREEN webpage: project description section

Figure 2-3 BeGREEN webpage news section: blog posts and project tweets (preview)

Website contents are regularly updated by project manager publishing news, submitted deliverables, and partners dissemination activities. To ease accessibility, the website content has been split in the following sections:

- Home, is the main page of BeGREEN website, which enables an easier browsing of the website content. It also contains links to the social media channels.
- About, contains an overall description of this project, presenting the BeGREEN vision, concept, innovation, demonstrators, and impact.
- News, includes relevant news and blog posts about BeGREEN activities and results, which will also be posted on BeGREEN social media channels to increase the project visibility.
- Deliverables, publishes project's submitted public deliverables.
- Disseminations, contains all disseminations including publications, talks and events, open-source contributions as well as the project's contributions to the standardisation activities.
- Consortium, introduces BeGREEN project partners.
- Contact, contains a contact form to provide a contact channel for all relevant communications to the BeGREEN consortium, and introduces project coordinator, project manager, and technical coordinator.

To measure the impact of BeGREEN project website, performance statistics are collected, such as: number of users visiting the website, number of sessions, average session duration, bounce rate, etc.

2.1.2 X (Twitter)

X (Twitter) is one of the most popular social networks and is widely used by the scientific community as a tool to communicate their results. In the same way as other SNS and previous 5G-PPP projects, BeGREEN has already set up a X account (<https://twitter.com/SNSBeGREEN>) with the aim of providing information about the ongoing activities throughout the project lifetime. Figure 2-4 shows a screenshot of the main BeGREEN X page.

Figure 2-4 BeGREEN project Twitter account

2.1.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn has established itself as a business and employment-oriented social network. Since LinkedIn is tailored for professionals, it is well suited to communicate the activities and contributions carried out in BeGREEN project. To that end, BeGREEN project management has created a project specific page (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/sns-begreen-project-613259250/>) whose main purpose is to open BeGREEN target audience. The LinkedIn page intends to foster discussions on relevant aspects of the project, advertise news and events, and collect stakeholder' opinions. Figure 2-5 shows a screenshot of the LinkedIn page.

Figure 2-5 BeGREEN project LinkedIn account

2.1.4 YouTube

YouTube is the most popular video-sharing platform in the world. Thus, it is the perfect social channel to broadcast the main activities carried out in the project. For that reason, BeGREEN hosts a YouTube channel that provides video content produced by the project to stakeholders at this address (<https://www.youtube.com/@snsbegreen>). Figure 2-6 shows BeGREEN's YouTube channel.

Figure 2-6 BeGREEN YouTube channel

2.1.5 Partners social channels

In addition to the project specific social media channel, BeGREEN consortium partners are encouraged to post related news and breakthroughs of the project regularly. Figure 2-7 shows some examples.

Figure 2-7 Examples of dissemination of BeGREEN news via partners (Accelleran, i2CAT) social media channels

2.1.6 Social Media Statistics

Project management keeps track of social media posts and statistics. Figure 2-8 shows the history of BeGREEN website hits, on months based, for the last we months. Furthermore, Figure 2-9 shows the number of hits in the first half of month February 2024, and Figure 2-10 indicates the busiest day for the website in terms of visits. Figure 2-11 and Figure 2-12 show BeGREEN LinkedIn and X accounts analytics.

Figure 2-8 BeGREEN website hits: 12 months period

Figure 2-9 BeGREEN website hits during the first 15 days of February 2024

Figure 2-10 BeGREEN website busiest day so far (in terms of visits): 152 hits on September 15, 2023

Figure 2-11 Latest analytics and stats of BeGREEN LinkedIn page

Figure 2-12 BeGREEN X account analytics

2.1.7 Newsletters

BeGREEN Newsletter #1 was released on 15th September 2023 with highlights of some project's results, ongoing activities, and disseminations. Specifically, the sections addressed covered:

- BeGREEN General Info
- BeGREEN Consortium
- BeGREEN Technical Introduction
- BeGREEN Proposed Architecture
- BeGREEN Reference Use Cases
- BeGREEN Demonstration Plans
- BeGREEN News

The newsletter can be accessed on the project website¹, and the title page is shown in Figure 2-13.

Figure 2-13 Announcement of BeGREEN's first newsletter

¹ <https://s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/cdn.webfactore.co.uk/10788-begreen+newsletter+1.pdf>

2.2 Scientific publications

To generate awareness and induce constructive comments and feedback from the scientific and industrial research community. BeGREEN will target high-level IEEE conferences and peer-reviewed journals related to the project's topics. We will also target top peer-reviewed journals, including, amongst others, IEEE Communications Magazine, and IEEE Transaction on Networking. The project targets to have more than 10 publications submitted per year in such journals and/or conferences. BeGREEN partners will organise own events and get speaking slots at important conferences and exhibitions. Where possible, the project will take advantage of partners' or European Commission presence at international or regional events. A set of presentation slides, relevant graphics and posters will be prepared to support consortium partners in such activities.

To raise awareness within the consortium about dissemination opportunities in relevant conferences, an excel file named 'BeGREEN Dissemination Opportunities' is shared on the project repository that contains a list of upcoming conferences. This is being periodically updated. The project also creates a 'Dissemination Tracking Tool', that is an Excel file for keeping the record of all project disseminations related details.

The publications achieved during the period are described in the following subsections, following a chronological order.

2.2.1 Journal paper published in Sensors

The paper is titled "On the Design of a Network Digital Twin for the Radio Access Network in 5G and Beyond" authored by Irene Vilà, Oriol Sallent and Jordi Pérez-Romero is published in Sensors 2023, 23, 1197 (<https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031197>). The paper content is related to UPC's work in WP4. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

"A Network Digital Twin (NDT) is a high-fidelity digital mirror of a real network. Given the increasing complexity of 5G and beyond networks, the use of an NDT becomes useful as a platform for testing configurations and algorithms prior to their application in the real network, as well as for predicting the performance of such algorithms under different conditions. While an NDT can be defined for the different subsystems of the network, this paper proposes an NDT architecture focusing on the Radio Access Network (RAN), describing the components to represent and model the operation of the different RAN elements, and to perform emulations. Different application use cases are identified, and among them, the paper puts the focus on the training of Reinforcement Learning (RL) solutions for the RAN. For this use case, the paper introduces a framework aligned with O-RAN specifications and discusses the functionalities needed to integrate the NDT. This use case is illustrated with the description of a RAN NDT implementation used for training an RL-based capacity-sharing solution for network slicing. Presented results demonstrate that the implemented RAN NDT is a suitable platform to successfully train the RL solution, achieving service-level agreement satisfaction values above 85%."

2.2.2 Conference paper at EuCNC'23

The consortium prepared a paper entitled "BeGREEN: Beyond 5G Energy Efficient Networking by Hardware Acceleration and AI-Driven Management of Network Functions", which was accepted at the EuCNC'23 (Gothenburg - Sweden, 6-9 June 2023). The paper was a joint effort by M. Ghoraiishi (GIGASYS), M. Catalan-Cid (i2CAT), V. Sark (IHP), J. Gutierrez Teran (IHP), O. Sallent (UPC), G. Bielsa (TSA), J. F. Esteban-Rivas (TSA) and S. Pryor (ACC). The paper describes BeGREEN's technical scope and objectives, aiming at improving energy efficiency of the beyond 5G (B5G) networks. The paper presented by M. Ghoraiishi (GIGASYS), project manager, at the conference.

2.2.3 Journal paper at IEEE Communications Magazine

The paper "Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) Experimentation Platform: Design and Datasets" by J. X. Salvat Lozano, J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Zanzi, A. Garcia-Saavedra, and X. Costa-Perez was accepted at IEEE Communications Magazine and published in Volume: 61, Issue: 9, September 2023. The paper is related to NEC's work in WP4. Specifically, the paper presents the testbed and datasets that will be later used to develop the solutions in T4.2 and T4.3. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

"The Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Alliance is driving the latest evolution of RAN deployments, moving from traditionally closed and dedicated hardware implementations toward virtualized instances running over shared platforms characterized by open interfaces. Such progressive decoupling of radio software components from the hardware paves the road for future efficient and cost-effective RAN deployments. Nevertheless, there are many open aspects toward the successful implementation of O-RAN networks, such as the real-time configuration of the network parameters to maximize performance, how to reliably share processing units among multiple virtualized base station (vBS) instances, how to palliate their energy consumption, or how to deal with the couplings between vRANs and other services co-located at the edge. Intending to shed light on these aspects, in this article, we showcase the design principles of an O-RAN compliant testbed, and present different datasets collected over a wide set of experiments, which are made public to foster research in this field."

IEEE Communications Magazine is ranked 4th out of 88 at JCR Telecommunications 2022.

2.2.4 Conference paper at CloudNet'23

The paper entitled "Understanding the Performance and Power Saving Tradeoffs of Server Sleep States" by A. Griffiths, A. Morsman and P. Veitch from BT was accepted at IEEE International Conference on Cloud Networking 2023 (CloudNet'23), which took place 1–3 November 2023 in New York Area (USA). The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

"With the growing use of software-based networking functions run on servers and the increased pressure to save power, it is more important than ever for telecommunications companies to fully leverage the power saving tools available on this form of hardware. It is often the case that servers spend a disproportionate amount of time in an idle state; therefore, we investigate a range of server settings which enable idle servers to enter sleep states. Although these settings have been accessible for some time, they are generally underutilised. We run tests on Intel architecture (IA) x86 servers to measure the potential power savings of different sleep states, considering this against the cost in exit latency. We present a comprehensive breakdown of the pros and cons of each sleep state, ultimately allowing them to be maximally utilised in a telco environment with confidence. We find that the maximum additional power saving of all the considered sleep states comes from core C-state, with a maximum ~80% processor saving when idle. Package C-states realise an additional power saving but comes at the cost of an increased exit latency."

2.2.5 Journal paper at IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials

The paper entitled "A Tutorial on the Characterisation and Modelling of Low Layer Functional Splits for Flexible Radio Access Networks in 5G and Beyond" by J. Pérez-Romero, O. Sallent, A. Gelonch, X. Gelabert, B. Klaiqi, M. Kahn and D. Campoy was accepted at IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials. The paper is related to UPC's work in WP2. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

"The centralization of baseband (BB) functions in a radio access network (RAN) towards data processing centres is receiving increasing interest as it enables the exploitation of resource pooling

and statistical multiplexing gains among multiple cells, facilitates the introduction of collaborative techniques for different functions (e.g., interference coordination), and more efficiently handles the complex requirements of advanced features of the fifth generation (5G) new radio (NR) physical layer, such as the use of massive multiple input multiple output (MIMO). However, deciding the functional split (i.e., which BB functions are kept close to the radio units and which BB functions are centralized) embraces a trade-off between the centralization benefits and the fronthaul costs for carrying data between distributed antennas and data processing centres. Substantial research efforts have been made in standardization fora, research projects and studies to resolve this trade-off, which becomes more complicated when the choice of functional splits is dynamically achieved depending on the current conditions in the RAN. This paper presents a comprehensive tutorial on the characterisation, modelling and assessment of functional splits in a flexible RAN to establish a solid basis for the future development of algorithmic solutions of dynamic functional split optimisation in 5G and beyond systems. First, the paper explores the functional split approaches considered by different industrial fora, analysing their equivalences and differences in terminology. Second, the paper presents a harmonized analysis of the different BB functions at the physical layer and associated algorithmic solutions presented in the literature, assessing both the computational complexity and the associated performance. Based on this analysis, the paper presents a model for assessing the computational requirements and fronthaul bandwidth requirements of different functional splits. Last, the model is used to derive illustrative results that identify the major trade-offs that arise when selecting a functional split and the key elements that impact the requirements.”

IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials is ranked 1st out of 88 at JCR Telecommunications 2022.

2.2.6 Journal paper at IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications

The paper “AIRIC: Orchestration of virtualized radio access networks with noisy neighbours” by J. X. Salvat Lozano, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Li, and X. Costa Perez was accepted for publication in IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications. The paper is related to NEC’s work in T4.2. The paper presents an AI agent that allocates cores to different virtual Base Stations considering the computing overhead due to non-ideal isolation between instances. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Radio Access Networks virtualization (vRAN) is on its way becoming a reality driven by the new requirements in mobile networks, such as scalability and cost reduction. Unfortunately, there is no free lunch but a high price to be paid in terms of computing overhead introduced by noisy neighbors problem when multiple virtualized base station instances share computing platforms. In this paper, first, we thoroughly dissect the multiple sources of computing overhead in a vRAN, quantifying their different contributions to the overall performance degradation. Second, we design an AI-driven Radio Intelligent Controller (AIRIC) to orchestrate vRAN computing resources. AIRIC relies upon a hybrid neural network architecture combining a relation network (RN) and a deep Q-Network (DQN) such that: (i) the demand of concurrent virtual base stations is satisfied considering the overhead posed by the noisy neighbors problem while the operating costs of the vRAN infrastructure is minimized; and (ii) dynamically changing contexts in terms of network demand, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and the number of base station instances are efficiently supported. Our results show that AIRIC performs very closely to an offline optimal oracle, attaining up to 30% resource savings, and substantially outperforms existing benchmarks in service guarantees.”

IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications is ranked 2nd out of 88 at JCR Telecommunications 2022.

2.2.7 Journal paper at IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking

The paper “EdgeBOL: A Bayesian Learning Approach for the Joint Orchestration of vRANs and Mobile Edge

AI” by Ayala-Romero, Jose A., et al. was accepted for publication in IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking. The paper is related to NEC’s work in T4.3. The paper presents an agent that allocates radio resources from an edge AI application perspective. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Future mobile networks need to support intelligent services which collect and process data streams at the network edge, so as to offer real-time and accurate inferences to users. However, the widespread deployment of these services is hindered by the unprecedented energy cost they induce to the network, and by the difficulties in optimizing their end-to-end operation. To address these challenges, we propose a Bayesian learning framework for jointly configuring the service and the Radio Access Network (RAN), aiming to minimize the total energy consumption while respecting accuracy and latency service requirements. Using a fully-fledged prototype with a software-defined base station (vBS) and a GPU-enabled edge server, we profile a typical video analytics service and identify new performance trade-offs and optimization opportunities. Accordingly, we tailor the proposed learning framework to account for the (possibly varying) network conditions, user needs, and service metrics, and apply it to a range of experiments with real traces. Our findings suggest that this approach effectively adapts to different hardware platforms and service requirements, and outperforms state-of-the-art benchmarks based on neural networks.”.

IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking is ranked 44th out of 88 at JCR Telecommunications 2022.

2.2.8 IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology

The paper “Deep Learning-based Algorithm for Optimizing Relay User Equipment Activation in 5G Cellular Networks” by Juan Jesús Hernández-Carlón, Jordi Pérez-Romero, Oriol Sallent, Irene Vilà and Ferran Casadevall (UPC) has been accepted to IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology. The paper content is related to UPC work in WP4. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“This paper addresses the problem of optimally using the relay capabilities of user equipment (UE) to augment the radio access network (RAN) in 5G deployments and beyond. This can be particularly useful in coverage constrained scenarios, such as those using millimeter waves, due to the difficulty radio signals penetrate some structures. This can lead to signal blockages and high penetration losses when providing outdoor-to-indoor coverage. To overcome these limitations, the use of relay UEs (RUEs) is seen as a possible solution to effectively extend the coverage of a cellular network. In this context, this paper proposes a deep learning-based algorithm to optimize the decision regarding when RUEs should be activated and deactivated in accordance with the benefits they can provide for increasing the spectral efficiency and decreasing outage probability for the network users. The obtained results reveal a promising capability of the proposed solution to activate the most beneficial RUEs given the network conditions being experienced, leading to improvements of average spectral efficiency of 12.3% and reductions of outage probability of 89% with respect to the case without relays.”.

IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology is ranked 14th out of 88 at JCR Telecommunications 2022.

2.2.9 Conference Paper at ITMS’23

The paper entitled “Dimensionality Reduction for Optimization of Radio Base Station Transmission Based on Energy Efficiency” by J. Armstrong from LMI and E. Fallon from TUS was accepted at ITMS 2023 64th International Scientific Conference on Information Technology and Management Science of Riga Technical University, which took place 5–6 November 2023 in Riga (Latvia). The paper is related to LMI’s work in WP 4.2 where the technique described can increase the speed and efficiency of identifying the network functions that need to be optimized before activating or applying energy efficiency algorithms. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Traffic volumes in radio networks have increased exponentially over the last decade. While the efficiency of these networks has also improved minimizing energy use is an important challenge in the telecommunications industry. To ensure maximum energy efficiency it is necessary for the configuration of each element in the network is optimal at all times. Minimizing the amount of data that needs to be processed in order to identify entities in the network that are operating with low energy efficiency can provide increases in the speed of detection and reductions in the processing power and data storage required for this task. This work demonstrates how techniques for calculating the marginal contribution of individual features in a dataset can be effectively used to significantly reduce the amount of data that need to be processed to detect sub-optimally configured elements in the network that may need reconfiguration.”

2.2.10 Conference Paper at ICCAIS’23

The paper entitled “Exploiting Cell Similarities in a Radio Access Network to Enhance Explainability for Autonomic Network Management Systems” by J. Armstrong from LMI and S. Fallon and E. Fallon from TUS was accepted at the 12th International Conference on Control, Automation and Information Sciences (ICCAIS 2023), which took place 27–29 November 2023 in Hanoi (Vietnam). The paper is related to LMI’s work in WP 4.2 where the technique described can be used to increase the accuracy and applicability of inferences drawn from network data that are used to identify areas of the network where the potential gains from energy efficiency optimisation are greatest. The abstract of the paper reads as follows:

“Modern telecommunications networks are highly complex and require constant real-time autonomic configuration to maintain optimum efficiency. A key technique used in autonomic self-correcting networks is identifying elements in the network that are performing worse than other equivalent elements and applying configurations to the problematic elements which correlate with the better performance on the equivalent elements. Where autonomic re-configuration is carried out on this basis it is important that the autonomous agent (AA) can provide a human interpretable rationale for why it carried out the reconfiguration which in this instance is a reason for why it considers specific elements in the telecommunications network to be equivalent to each other. This paper investigates the utility of Explainable AI techniques to describe and evaluate affinities between elements in the network based on performance data.”

2.3 Organizing highly directed workshops

BeGREEN members are very active and feature a vast expertise in organising flagship conference workshops and special sessions in the technical areas of the project. For example, members of the project organized workshops in the last three EuCNCs. Following this consolidated strategy, BeGREEN is taking the lead in organizing international workshops in collaboration with other projects, as a premiere opportunity to present project results in a very interactive and formal environment.

Workshop at EuCNC’23

The workshop entitled “The role of AI in Edge 6G topologies” was accepted to EuCNC’23. The workshop intended to draw lessons learned and a strategic way forward from the following 5 EU funded R&D projects: BRAINE (Call ID: H2020-ECSEL-2019-2-RIA), VERGE (Call ID: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-05), ACES (Call ID: HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01), SmartEdge (Call ID: HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01) and BeGREEN. From BeGREEN side, O. Sallent (UPC) participated in the drafting of the proposal. The focus of the workshop was established around the following challenges:

- Evolving open, secure and decentralised edge architectures to enable AI
- Heterogeneity and interoperability aspects for an integrated compute continuum and sustainable AI

solutions

- Closed-loop automation and cognition for the joint AI-driven orchestration of network, radio and compute resources at the Edge.
- Extreme and conflicting KPIs at network and compute level.
- KPIs versus KVLs tradeoffs in Edge resource orchestration.
- Security, privacy, trustworthiness, and data sovereignty in distributed edge topologies.
- Decentralised edge intelligence and advanced learning algorithms.
- Explainable AI/ML algorithms, to identify which network functions need to be optimised and the contributory factors that lead to this need for optimization.

The structure of the workshop embraced a first part based on presentations of two-page papers by each of the organizing projects to set the scene. The second act counted with Invited Speakers presentations to broaden the perspective. Finally, the workshop included a final panel featuring the Technical Managers (or key contributors) of the five projects.

The Workshop took place on 6th June 2023. The final programme of the Workshop included 4 distinguished invited speakers:

- Dr. Xueli An, Head of 6G Network Architecture Research Group at Huawei, “6G: The Next Horizon - From Connected People, Things to Connected Intelligence”.
- Dr. Miquel Payaró, Senior Researcher and Director of Open Innovation and Science at CTTC, “Experimental validation of edge-hosted AIML approaches in B5G/6G networks”.
- Dr. Dan Warren, Director of Advanced Network Research at Samsung Research UK, “AI for Networks, Networks for AI”.
- Dr. Fernando Ramos, Associate Professor (University of Lisbon) & Senior Researcher (INESC-ID), “6G: a networking challenge”.

Figure 2-14 Dr. Dan Warren and Dr. Xueli An during their invited talks

A very interesting panel discussion closed the workshop, gathering 30+ attendants. The discussion was

around the following questions:

- Why is the combination of 6G and Edge so important for Europe ?, Which early adopter applications do you foresee?
- Massive Edge AI will still require data collection, curation, storage, analytics, training, seamless inferencing in distributed environments. What are the main challenges that need to be addressed?
- How will AI drive sustainability of 6G, energy efficiency?
- How will the conflicts between the various AI engines (sensing, communicating, interpreting, acting) and running at the edge be resolved?

Overall, the Workshop was a very good opportunity to disseminate BeGREEN's objectives and approach, interact with other projects, discuss with other researchers and identify possible paths of new collaborations (e.g., with NVIDIA, thanks to the fact that J. J. Vegas Olmos attended the Workshop).

2.3.2 Expert panel discussion at WCNC'24

The panel is titled "Energy Efficiency in Wireless Communications Networks, 5G to 6G Challenges and Opportunities", proposed by Mir Ghoraishi (BeGREEN project manager) and Chiara Lombardo (6Green technical manager). There are four European projects involved in this panel as, BeGREEN, 6Green (SNS), Verge (SNS), and Greenedge (ITN). The panel will discuss the following issues related to the energy efficiency and sustainability of future networks:

- Energy efficiency in wireless network, discuss the challenges and opportunities
- Major energy consumers in wireless network and their evolution from 5G to 6G
- Metrics of energy efficiency in current and future mobile networks
- Challenges of using AI for improving network energy efficiency: AI sustainability, AI energy consumption
- Evolution of the service-based architecture (SBA), from 5G to 6G, to improve energy efficiency#
- The role of Open RAN paradigm in sustainability and energy efficiency enhancement of the network

The session starts with presentations by each panelist, as listed below, followed by the panel discussion:

- "Sustainability as a Key Criterion for Network Design on the Path to 6G" by Dr Volker Ziegler (Senior Advisor, Chief Architect, Nokia)
- "Sustainability in 6G, Challenges and Opportunities" by Prof. Merouane Debbah (Professor at Khalifa University, Director of the KU 6G Research Centre)
- "Sustainable AI for mobile networks: challenges and GREENEDGE and VERGE projects solutions" by Dr Paolo Dini (Senior Researcher and Coordinator of Sustainable Artificial Intelligence Research Unit, CTTC/CERCA)
- "A Win-Win Approach towards 6G Sustainability: 6Green green economical approach for infrastructure and virtual stakeholders to join forces towards a common efficiency goal" by Dr Chiara Lombardo (Researcher at University of Genoa)
- "What ORAN Can Offer to Facilitate Enhancing Energy Efficiency in 6G: BeGREEN ORAN based intelligent solutions for enhanced energy efficiency in radio access" by Dr Mir Ghoraishi (CEO and Project Manager, Gigasys Solutions)

The panel is posted on the project LinkedIn and X, and will be posted on the project website soon. Figure

2-15 shows the announcement on project's social media.

Figure 2-15 BeGREEN co-organised expert panel discussion in WCNC 2024 (announcement)

Expert panel at ICC 2024

Mir Ghoraiishi (Gigasys Solutions) is invited to take part as panelist in the “Third International Workshop on Green and Sustainable Networking”, in IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)². The full programme of this workshop is yet to be published online.

Workshop and booth proposals for EuCNC 2024

BeGREEN partners have been active in preparing workshop proposals. A full day workshop proposal was submitted, titled “Sustainability: Paving the Road to a Sustainable 6G”, where Mir Ghoraiishi (Gigasys Solutions) is the co-proposer and co-organiser. This workshop was proposed with the participation of four SNS projects: BeGREEN, 6Green, Verge and Exiegence, and a Horizon Europe project Zeros-Swarm. In addition, 6G-IA Vision Working Group, and SNS JU Sustainability Task Force are participating as well. The program includes dedicated sessions to 6GIA Vision WG (to discuss the recent white paper on sustainability) and SNS JU Sustainability TF (on holistic sustainability impact framework for SNS JU), two keynote talks by distinguished speakers, a session for invited presentations from participating projects, following by an expert panel discussion. We look forward to receiving the evaluation result of the proposal.

BeGREEN project and partners are involved in at least three more workshop proposals for EuCNC 2024, as invited presenters. In addition, the project is preparing a booth proposal that includes several demonstrations. The deadline for booth proposals is in March 2024.

2.4 Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives

The members of the consortium have been, and are very active, in organizing activities related to the BeGREEN research areas. These constitute very important forums for presenting the achieved results to the scientific and industrial communities. Similarly, the BeGREEN project members are highly involved in international programme committees and editorial boards of key conferences and journals. BeGREEN members' participation in joint initiatives among related projects in the ICT program is anticipated. BeGREEN

² <https://icc2024.ieee-icc.org/workshop/ws-11-third-international-workshop-green-and-sustainable-networking-greenet>

has already taken the initiative to make a cluster of related topic projects to boost publicising the project activities and the dissemination of the results.

ETSI research conference

The ETSI Research Conference was held at ETSI Headquarters in Sophia-Antipolis from 6th to 8th February 2023. The conference coined the title “Maximizing the Impact of European 6G Research through Standardization” and gathered over 160 attendees.

The event enabled the research community to learn about the latest European research projects, and the plans for future activities and funding as well as guidance on when, where and how to get involved in standardization. In turn, the standards community was able to learn about the latest innovative technology research areas that may have an impact on their future work, as well as making early connections to projects of relevance to their work. In addition, the ETSI Research Conference presented success stories and examples of research being integrated into standards, as well as indications from the standards community as to where they would seek research input to help move next generation standardization forward.

Overall, this face-to-face event provided an exceptional opportunity for the research community to come together with industry representatives and standardization experts to discuss future technology research and links to standardization developments.

BeGREEN presented at the conference an overview of the project with focus on standardisation plan. The presentation took place within the specific session devoted to Stream A projects. As depicted in Figure 2-16, the session included a 10 minutes presentation of each project followed by a 30 minutes panel discussion.

- 14:00 – 15:30: SESSION 5: Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) Projects Part 1 (Stream A, Strand A1 - A7)
 Chaired by Kostas Trichias, 6G-IA
- The SNS Phase 1 (2022) Stream A projects target the development of smart communication components, systems, and networks following the evolution of 5G systems. These projects follow an evolutionary path towards the development of 6G networks, relying on the development of an intermediate technology point. As such, the solutions developed by these projects are closer to the current standardization activities of 3GPP and other relevant SDOs and stand a chance to impact standardization in the short to mid-term. To achieve that, clear technology evolution directions and concrete targets with regards to standardization organizations and Work Groups are needed, aligned with the current SDO roadmaps. In this session, each project will present its key objectives, the technologies with potential for significant standardization impact and their standardization plans, and commonly discuss how to maximize short to mid-term impact in relevant SDOs.*
- 14:00 Project Presentation: 5G-STARDUST
Mohamed El Jaafari
 - 14:10 Project Presentation: ACROSS
Ioannis Markopoulos
 - 14:20 Project Presentation: BeGREEN
Mir Ghoraiishi
 - 14:30 Project Presentation: NANCY
Alexandros Apostolos Boulogeorgos and Panagiotis Sarigiannidis
 - 14:40 Project Presentation: SEASON
Filippo Cugini and Ramon Casellas
 - 14:50 Project Presentation: VERGE
Oriol Sallent
 - 15:00 Q&A and Panel Discussion with the session speakers, moderated by Kostas Trichias

Figure 2-16 Structure of session for SNS Stream A projects

2.5 Industry exhibitions

The project has been actively searching for opportunities to present project findings. As mentioned above, a proposal for booth exhibitions for EuCNC 2024 is being prepared. BeGREEN brochures were shared at the booth of consortium partners in Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2023, and similarly will be exhibited in MWC 2024. Partners who have a booth at MWC and have their booth available for BeGREEN brochure are: Acceleran, RunEL, Parallel Wireless, i2CAT (QR code and logo), ARM (QR code and logo). The SNS JU

community is informed regarding BeGREEN plan for MWC presence.

2.6 Dissemination through training and personal mobility

BeGREEN will increase the number of students trained in the areas covered by the project. MSc or PhD students working in the project will carry their ideas into their future workplaces and academic institutions, thus increasing the reach of BeGREEN impact.

Seminar “The Way to 6G”

The seminar “The Way to 6G” was held from 24th to 30th January 2023 at UPC premises in Barcelona. It took advantage of the no-classes period after termination of first semester exams and initiation of second semester. A total of 16 students registered to the seminar, which was lectured along 5 days with 4 or 5 hours per day, totalling 22 hours.

The seminar addressed the way from 5G to Beyond 5G and eventually 6G through the major technological components envisaged in this roadmap. Emphasis was placed on the need that Beyond 5G and 6G take a holistic view to provide evolving radio networks that not only accommodate increasing traffic and service levels but also consider power consumption as a factor. Students gained awareness about the relevance of involving energy-efficiency principles across the system design.

Seminar “Embedding Artificial Intelligence in Beyond 5G Radio Access Networks”

In a visit of Oriol Sallent (UPC) to Indiana University at Bloomington (USA), a seminar disseminating key elements associated to BeGREEN was organised. The seminar gathered 25 attendees from the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing and Engineering.

The visit offered a unique opportunity to meet several faculty staff with research interests closely related to BeGREEN and several ad-hoc meetings were interleaved with the seminar. These included a meeting with Dr. Andrew Lukefahr, another meeting with Dr. Prateek Sharma and another meeting with Prof. Martin Swamy, Chair of Intelligent Systems Engineering department. The overall visit was hosted by Dr. Dingwen Tao. In all cases, high interest for BeGREEN was expressed and possible visits from Dr. Tao and Prof. Swamy to UPC in Barcelona were discussed.

SNS JU webinar

The SNS JU office and the 6G-IA office organized a series of webinars to introduce the SNS JU Call 1 projects. The purpose of the webinars was to get the chance to introduce the project’s focus, main objectives, activities and goals and to provide additional useful information and insights. The initiative was launched in a series of four lunchtime webinars:

SNS Lunchtime Webinar 1: Stream B5, C & D projects addressing 6G Holistic System, SNS experimental Infrastructures & SNS Large scale Trials and Pilots; Wednesday 15/02/2023 @ 12.00

SNS Lunchtime Webinar 2: Stream A projects addressing: Smart Communication Components, Systems and Networks for 5G Evolution Systems; Monday 20/02/2023 @ 12.00

SNS Lunchtime Webinar 3: Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services and Security; Thursday 23/02/2023 @ 12.00

SNS Lunchtime Webinar 4: Stream B2 & B3 projects addressing: Wireless Communications and Signal Processing & Communication Infrastructure and Devices; Monday 06/03/2023 @ 12.00

BeGREEN participated to Webinar 2, as shown in the agenda depicted in Figure 2-17.

Webinar 2 Agenda				
Time	Call	Project Acronym / Presentation	Presenter	Presenter Affiliation & project role
12.00 - 12.05	N/A	Intro & Welcome	Kostas Trichias	6G-IA, SNS-ICE Coordinator
12.05 - 12.10	N/A	6G-IA Welcome and SNS programme message	Colin Willcock	6G SNS GB Chair, 6G-IA Chair
12.10 - 12.15	N/A	SNS JU organization & Stream A description	Chiara Mazzone	Programme Officer, SNS JU
12.15 - 12.30	A-01-01	BeGREEN	Mir Ghoraishi	Gigasys Solutions , Project Manager
12.30 - 12.45	A-01-02	5G-STARBUCK	Tomaso de Cola	German Aerospace Center (DLR), Project Coordinator
12.45 - 13.00	A-01-03	SEASON	Filippo Cugini	CNIT, Project Coordinator
13.00 - 13.15	A-01-04	6Green	Dr. Chiara Lombardo	CNIT - Technical Manager
13.15 - 13.25	BREAK 10'			
13.25 - 13.40	A-01-05	VERGE	Oriol Sallent	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Project Coordinator
13.40 - 13.55	A-01-06	NANCY	Panagiotis Sarigiannidis Alexandross Boulogeorgos	Project Coordinator Technical manager, University of Western Macedonia
13.55 - 14.10	A-01-07	ACROSS	Dimitris Klonidis	Ubitech, Technical Manager
14.10 - 14.25	N/A	Q&A	Kostas Trichias	6G-IA, SNS-ICE Coordinator
14.25 - 14.30	N/A	End of Webinar		

Figure 2-17 Agenda of SNS Lunchtime Webinar 2

2.7 Datasets published

Dataset associated to the paper "Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) Experimentation Platform: Design and Datasets" by J. X. Salvat Lozano, J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Zanzi, A. Garcia-Saavedra, and X. Costa-Perez was published at IEEE Dataport: <https://iee-dataport.org/documents/o-ran-experimental-evaluation-datasets>. The dataset contains traces from experiments that test different configurations in computing and radio in deployed vBSs. All the datasets are in CSV format and can be easily loaded using pandas.

3 External Liaison

3.1 Participation in SNS JU

BeGREEN partners and delegates have been active in collaboration with other SNS and 6GIA projects given the framework of collaboration (Collaboration Agreement) that has been signed by the consortium. In such framework the information exchange and other sorts of interactions with peer projects are easily achievable. BeGREEN consortium is experienced as they have been active in the community for the past years in 5GPPP projects. Active liaison with SNS and 5GPPP activities, and the interactions with other projects within this framework is led by the Project Manager from BeGREEN side.

The project has representation in the Steering Board (Coordinator and Project Manager), and Technology Board (Technical Coordinator and Project Manager) and contribute fully to the actions emanating from these fora.

3.1.1 Participation in SNS Working Groups

The SNS Initiative Steering Board (SB) kick-off meeting took place in Athens, 5th September 2023, hosted by Space Hellas. Around 40 people attended the meeting, with the vast majority of Project Coordinators of the 35 on-going SNS JU projects present at the meeting. Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS) represented BeGREEN at the meeting. The meeting was very informative about the role of the SB and its overall objectives. Concerning the SNS Projects Working Groups (WGs), 3 WGs were approved. Participants to the WGs are listed in Table 3-1. The activities of these WGs are formalised in fortnightly, or monthly, WG meetings. These might include project presentations, joint white paper preparations, joint event (e.g., workshop, panel, etc.) proposals, and so on.

Table 3-1 BeGREEN Consortium Participation in SNS WGs

Working Group	Participants
Architecture	GIGASYS, LMI, NEC
Reliable software networks	-
Test, Measurements and Validation	TSA, GIGASYS

3.1.2 Participation to 6G-IA Working Groups

As it is observed in Table 3-2, the project already has representatives in most of the 6G-IA working groups to channelise the project contributions, and in occasions, edit position papers, deliverables and reports from the working groups, proactively driving working groups closely related to their project goals.

Table 3-2 BeGREEN Consortium Participation in 6G-IA WGs

Working Group	Participants
5G for CAM	-
Open Smart Networks and Services	GIGASYS, I2CAT, LMI, TSA, NEC, REL
Pre-Standardization	TSA, NEC, GIGASYS
Security	TSA, GIGASYS
Trials	GIGASYS, LMI

Vision and Societal Challenges	TSA
Women in Telecommunications and Research	-

4 Summary and Conclusions

This document has described BeGREEN's dissemination and communication actions conducted from the start of the project until the end of M13. The final report of actions and achievements will be reported in D6.5 due in M30, together with report on impact and exploitation.

The comparison of the achievements against the target KPIs is summarised in Table 4-1. Being at M13 and having 17 months ahead BeGREEN's own assessment is that communication and dissemination actions are in good track. In the cases that the figures are well behind the targets (e.g., videos posted on YouTube channel, participation in industry events), it is expected that as the project progresses and relevant results are attained such opportunities will arise in a more natural way. Regarding publications, it is worth highlighting that, beyond the number of publications, which is in good track to achieve the targets, 4 high impact journal publications have been achieved (i.e., ranking 1st, 2nd, 4th, and 14th out of 88 in JCR Telecommunications 2022).

Table 4-1 BeGREEN Achievements Against Targets at the End of M13

Type of Action	Target KPI	Achievements
Website & social media	At least 2 newsletters per year, targeting at least 200 followers on X and LinkedIn, 3000 access to website, 10 videos posted on YouTube channel	1 newsletter 13 connections on LinkedIn 11 followers on X 1069 website visits in February alone
Scientific publications	At least 15	10 publications
Organisation of highly directed workshops	At least 2 workshops as organisers (1 as lead) At least 3 workshops as participants	1 workshop as organiser
Participation in 5G/B5G initiatives	At least 5 participations	1 participation
Industry exhibitions	At least participation in 10 industrial events with project visibility	2 participation
Dissemination through training and personal mobility	At least 3 actions	3 actions
Datasets published	At least 2	1 dataset

Bibliography

[1] "SNS-JU BeGREEN Project," 2016. [Online]. Available: www.sns-begreen.com.